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LETTER OF PUBLICATION

To, Authors,

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Greetings!

As our peer editorial review process, It's a great pleasure to inform you that,
Your Manuscript Entitle, **“The Manuscript as an Archival Document Preserving National Identity and Memory, and Contributing to Local and National Historiography through Museum Institutions: – The Mujahid Museum of Sidi Bel Abbès, in Algeria, as a Case Study”** has been accepted and considered for Publication in our **TECHNICAL COMMUNICATION** in Volume No. 26– issue 1-(2026).

Thank you for submitting your work to this journal.

Best Regards,

IVAN

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